

Contents lists available at <https://susagr.uz/index.php/ojs/issue/view/8>

Sustainable Agriculture

journal homepage: <https://susagr.uz/index.php/ojs>

Improvement of the System of Growing Agricultural Products on Forest Fund Lands

Umirzok Kholiyorov^a

^aPhD, Senior Lecturer, the department of “Management and Tourism”, “Tashkent institute of irrigation and agricultural mechanization engineers”, National research university, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

forestry, natural resource, afforestation and landscaping, digital management, rent, medicinal plants, conservation.

ABSTRACT

This article describes a number of problems and shortcomings in growing agricultural products on forest lands and the effective use of forest areas, adopted regulations and resolutions to eliminate them, as well as a number of positive consequences of the reforms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Further development of the country's forestry sector in recent years, full utilization of the rich potential of forest resources and ensuring their rational use, increasing the efficiency of forest fund land use, introducing advanced scientific and technical achievements into the sector, actively attracting foreign investment, and developing ecological tourism.

At the same time, despite the large-scale reforms being carried out, a number of problems and shortcomings remain in the effective use of forest areas. Including:

- insufficient scientific research on the creation, selection, and propagation of new tree species resistant to abnormally hot and drought conditions for afforestation and landscaping by biotechnological methods;
- no electronic database and maps of the state of forest fund lands and flora using intelligent, artificial intelligence software in the digital management of forests have been developed;
- insufficient attention is paid to the use of modern technical means in the implementation of forestry measures. Technical means and mechanisms for digging, planting seedlings, and carrying out other measures have not been developed;
- a transparent system using market mechanisms and information and communication technologies has not been fully implemented in the lease of forest fund lands;
- Currently, pastures are not fully provided with irrigation sources (wells). In pastures close to water sources, there are cases of decline due to an increase in the number of livestock.
- insufficient organization of work on the protection of existing natural forest areas in the reserve of district khokimiyats and at the disposal of other economic entities.

- The constant relocation of beehives leads to the death of bee colonies. (beekeeping forests should be created)

- a guaranteed market for the sale of medicinal plant raw materials grown in the republic, as well as a mechanism for supplying natural and cultivated medicinal plants grown in neighboring republics to domestic processing enterprises, has not been formed.

- insufficient attention is paid to the protection of wild animals on forest fund lands, increasing their numbers and species, and developing hunting tourism.

Studies show that forests occupy a significant part of the natural resources available in our republic and also have a unique production potential. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the effective use of lands of the country's forest fund, which is considered the most valuable natural resource, and the development of the forestry sector. Also, water, flora, and fauna in the forestry system, as an invaluable natural resource, are of great importance for the development of our economy.

In addition, the issue of "Improving the system of rational use of natural resources and environmental protection, providing for the rational use of land and water resources, forest fund" is defined as a separate direction as a priority area for the implementation of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture for 2020-2030, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5853 dated October 23, 2019. At the same time, the main attention is paid to improving the forest resource management system, introducing modern methods for their assessment and monitoring, as well as developing a system of criteria and indicators that ensure the accounting of forest resources at market prices.

* Corresponding author. umirzok1102@gmail.com (U. Kholiyorov)

E-mail addresses: umirzok1102@gmail.com (U. Kholiyorov)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18348403>

Received 30 October 2025; Received in revised form 25 November 2025; Accepted 1 December 2025

Available online 15 December 2025

ISSN 2181-9408/© 2025 The Authors. Published by “TIAME” NRU. The journal “Sustainable Agriculture” is registered in the Press Agency of Uzbekistan on the 12th of February in 2018 (license № 0957). In 2019, the journal is included in the list of recommended scientific publications by the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

From this point of view, the scientific, methodological, and theoretical aspects of the modernization of forestry and the development of transformational processes in the industry, natural resources in the forestry system, their reproduction, methods of sustainable management, and increasing the efficiency of their use require in-depth study. Analysis of the work carried out to date on modernization and structural changes in the industry, reforming the system of production of agricultural products, processing of natural and forest resources, additional use and provision of services, identifying the state and possibilities of their diversification, assessing the organizational, economic, and legal relations established and existing in the industry vertically and horizontally, the effectiveness and state of their management, studying experience in this area, further deepening structural changes in the forestry system, developing the activities of new integrated structures providing production and services, using natural resources in forestry, their restoration, conducting research on the development of the system of state regulation and management of the industry is becoming relevant.

Uzbekistan is considered one of the countries with low forest cover and in the past consisted of tugai forests, wild poplars, and other broad-leaved trees and shrubs. However, in recent decades, a steady decrease in their number has been observed under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors. Saxaul and desert shrubs growing in sandy soil areas of the republic's forest fund play an extremely important role in protecting soil from wind erosion. On the territory of our country, relatively large forest areas are located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Navoi and Bukhara regions, while relatively small forests are located in the Fergana Valley, Samarkand and Syrdarya regions. In general, in our country, unlike other states of Central Asia, it is mainly used as a means of protection, that is, in the fight against desertification, in the prevention of natural disasters that may occur in various forms, in the protection of agricultural land, in the protection of pastures used in the livestock industry. That is, the noted circumstances, along with the development of agriculture, which is one of the leading sectors of our national economy, in particular, its livestock sector, play an important role in the conservation of water resources, which are extremely important in almost all sectors.

2. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

In order to eliminate these problems, in recent years, special attention has been paid to strengthening the regulatory framework of the sphere. In particular, 1 law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1 decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 5 resolutions, 21 resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, and about 40 roadmaps were adopted.

As a result of the organizational reforms carried out and the decrees and resolutions adopted, the attitude towards increasing the efficiency of forest fund land use in our republic has completely changed. All this contributed to the achievement of a number of positive results.

Including:

- management of the country's forest fund lands, ensuring their functioning as an integrated system, increases management efficiency and creates the basis for raising the achieved results to a qualitatively new level;

- developed and implemented modern mechanisms for the rational use, restoration, and protection of resources of the forest fund, in particular land, flora, and fauna, which are widespread in the republic and have been neglected for many years, used haphazardly and arbitrarily;

- the introduction of market mechanisms in the use of forest fund lands, the development of mutually beneficial cooperation, and the creation of a basis for obtaining additional income for the population living in areas close to forest fund lands;

- a system for strengthening the material base and deep processing of medicinal and healing plants has been created, including through the collection of medicinal plants and the creation of their cultivated plantations;

- an increase in the volume of agricultural production was achieved, in particular, in crop production, horticulture, beekeeping, meat and dairy products (fish farming, cattle breeding, sheep breeding), and other types of products.

In particular, during 2017-2022, the total area of agricultural production on forest fund lands in the region increased from 932.2 hectares in 2017 to 936.7 hectares in 2022, or achieved a small increase.

If we analyze by crops, then in 2017 the area of grain and leguminous crops was 438.3 hectares, in 2020 - 436.5 hectares, and in 2022 - 439.2 hectares. The area of vegetable and melon crops and potatoes by years was 71.6 ha, 71.3 ha, and 70.5 ha, respectively, while the area of orchards and walnut orchards was 300.3 ha, 295.3 ha, and 300.6 ha.

In Kashkadarya region, the volume of agricultural production on forest fund lands also has a small growth rate in accordance with the land area, which is explained by the specifics of the industry. In particular, in 2017, a total of 4997.2 tons of agricultural products were grown, including 1073.4 tons of grain and legumes, 1276.2 tons of vegetables and melons, 1541.2 tons of feed, and 1099.3 tons of fruits.

3. CONCLUSION.

In general, forest fund lands, as an untapped hidden potential of our country, have been neglected for many years and have suffered some losses as a result of improper use.

Based on the above, it can be said that the lands of the forest fund are a potential resource of our republic, it is one of the largest sectors of the economy that performs such tasks as the preservation of biodiversity, stabilization of the ecological situation, development of the green economy, and at the same time, one of the most urgent tasks is the cultivation of food products using this land fund, ensuring employment of the population, and price stability in remote areas.

Therefore, the issue of increasing the efficiency of agricultural production, production volumes, and the level of resource saving on forest fund lands is one of the main tasks on the agenda in today's conditions of increasing national food security.

REFERENCES

- [1] Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. UP-5853 "On Approving the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030."
- [2] Berdiyev E.T., Saloxiddinov G.M., Xamrayev X.F. "Forestry" - Tashkent, Tashkent State Agrarian University Editorial and Publishing Department, 2012
- [3] Е.А.Бюллер. Организационно-экономический механизм устойчивого сельскохозяйственного лесопользования в регионе. Дис. канд. экон. наук: 08.00.05.-М.: РГБ, 2005.
- [4] Ботолов Н.А. Лесное хозяйство в системе АПК.-М.: Агропромиздат, 1987. 167 с.
- [5] Мурахтанов Е.С., Торцев Е.В., Котенков В.М. Организация и ведение хозяйства в сельских лесах, Брянск, 2001.
- [6] Романенко Г.О. О неотложных мерах по стабилизации и развитию аг-ропромышленного производства // АПК: экономика, управление.-1999.-№5.